

Ichnofabric oscillatory curves as an indicator of the tide-dominated depositional system, Samarinda area, Kutai Basin (Indonesia)

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Abstract

The overall purpose of this study was to reinterpret the paleoenvironmental processes in the Samarinda area, Kutai Basin, Indonesia. Ichnofabric methods are used for that. The bioturbation index (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), number of behavior (NB), penetration depth (PD), ichnofossil diameter (Dm), in ichnofabric units were scrutinized. The data were processed by principal component analysis (PCA). The main findings were (1) the PC-1 and PC-2 oscillatory curves, and (2) the phase between PC-1 and PC-2 curves (i.e., out of phase and in phase). The PC-1 curve was loaded by BI, ID, and NB and the PC-2 was loaded by PD and Dm. The generated curves were interpreted as the indicators of colonization window, organism mobility, and space using by the organism. The oscillatory pattern of curve suggested how the organism interact with the substrate are repeated that dictated routinely by the paleoenvironmental processes variation that suggested as the tide-dominated depositional system.

Keywords: bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, number of behavior, penetration depth, ichnofossil diameter, principal component analysis, oscillatory curves.

1. Introduction

The repetitive episodes of regression and transgression (Galloway, 1989) and/or inconstant of the relative intensity of fluvial, wave and tidal processes through time and space commonly occurred in the marginal marine systems. Accordingly, the possible evolutionary classification of coastal depositional systems is present (Boyd et al., 1992). Consequently, that has implication the previous depositional system that paleofluvial-marine interaction is recognized in Samarinda area, Kutai Basin (see Allen and Chambers, 1998; Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005). The implications are (1) not only delta can be developed in the study area, but it may to other coastal depositional systems (e.g., estuary, strandplain, lagoon) may be taken place; (2) large delta system that can contain the elements such as estuary and strandplain (c.f., Mahakam delta). As Galloway and Hobday (1996, p. 91) stated: "few processes or environments are unique to deltaic settings." Thus, it is critical to identify the scale observation within the larger context regional (see Dalrymple and Choi, 2007; Bhattacharya and Giosan, 2003; Boyd et al., 1992).

The essence of depositional systems is processes-related that placed as larger context regional product of associated depositional environments (see Galloway, 1989). The variation processes intensity that interacts there (e.g., physical, chemical and biological) will change dramatically through space and time in the transition zone. The physical processes (e.g., fluvial, tidal, wave; sediment movement) can be observed from lithofacies features and ichnofabric criteria (e.g., Arifullah et al., 2016). However, the

chemical (*e.g.*, paleosalinity, paleotemperature, paleo-oxygenation) and biological (*e.g.*, paleocommunity) processes can be observed from ichnofabric criteria only (*i.e.*, bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, number of behavior, penetration depth, and ichnofossil diameter) (Arifullah et al., 2016, 2017). Thus, the aim of this paper is (1) to depict the paleoenvironmental processes as the facets of the depositional system, (2) to demonstrate the options (*i.e.*, interpretations and methodology) in the basin analysis.

2. Geological setting

The research area is located in Samarinda, Indonesia (Figure 1) which deposited within the Kutai Basin. This basin bordered to the north by Sangkulirang strike-slip fault, to the south by Paternoster strike-slip fault. To the west, the basin is bounded by highly deformed and uplifted Paleogene sediments and Cretaceous metasediments that make up the Central Kalimantan Mountains and to the east by the Makassar Strait. Moreover, the research area is located in Samarinda Anticlinorium with respect to the edge of the Kutai Basin and major structural trend in the area. In addition, Samarinda area was depocenter during the Miocene (Moss and Chambers, 1999) which was interpreted as a deltaic depositional system (*e.g.*, Allen and Chambers, 1998; Bachtar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005).

Since the observed outcrops sited between Batuputih (Langhian age, Di Martino et al., 2015) and Stadion Palaran (Tortonian age, Di Martino et al., 2015), then those are deposited at Serravallian relatively or correlated with Middle Miocene. At that epoch, delta had prograde to the eastward that triggered by multiple inversion events (see Chambers and Daley, 1995).

3. Methods

3.1 Dataset

A total of 6 outcrops which 270,5 meters thick, exposed in a 100's meter-long lithological section was observed. The outcrops were oriented to NE-SW (Figure 1) which coincidence with Kutai Basin structural trend and dispersed in the northern part (*i.e.* BER-1 and BER-2) and the southern part (*i.e.* PAL-3, TAM-1, TAM-2, and MAN-2). A detailed observation and description of 381 ichnofabric units were conducted for every centimeter scale of beds. Each ichnofabric units were constituted by ichnometric variables includes bioturbation index; ichnofossil diversity and its behavior; penetration depth and maximum burrow diameter (see Arifullah et al., 2017).

3.2 Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

Before PCA was applied, all ichnometric variables (*i.e.* bioturbation index, ichnodiversity, number of behavior, penetration depth and burrow diameter) which measured in the different unit should be standardized (see Arifullah et al., 2017). The goal of principal component analysis (PCA) was to reduce the dimensionality of a data set consisting of a large number of interrelated ichnofabric variables to reveal the something hidden and simplified structures. Only the first few components would be important enough to be retained for interpretation and used to present the data (Keho, 2012). Consequently, it was reasonable to make sure how many PC was necessary to best describe the data and how to interpret them.

Figure 1 Geological map of Kalimantan (Hall and Nichols, 2002) and study area.

4. Results

4.1 Principal components

In the Figure 2a, loading plot PC-1 as being positively and mostly correlated with ichnodiversity ($r = 0.84$); number of behavior ($r = 0.81$) and bioturbation index ($r = 0.60$). Moreover, the correlation coefficient which lower than 0.4 (i.e. weakly positively correlated) was indicated by penetration depth and burrow diameter. Conversely, Figure 2b demonstrated that PC-2 was positively correlated with penetration depth ($r = 0.64$) and burrow diameter ($r = 0.68$). In addition, the weak correlation was indicated by bioturbation index, ichnodiversity and the number of behaviors. As the result, (1) the most important variables in explaining the PC-1 were ichnodiversity (ID), the number of behavior (NE) and bioturbation index (BI); (2) penetration depth (PD) and burrow diameter (Dm) were the most important variable that explained of PC-2.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2 (a) The loading of ichnometric variables in PC-1, (b) PC-2. Only variables which had coefficient correlation value more than or equal 0.4 were regards as significant loading

Explanation:
 Op = *Ophiomorpha*
 Ma = *Macaronichnus*
 Pa = *Paleophycus*
 Pl = *Planolites*
 Ch = *Chondrites*
 Sk = *Skolithos*
 Th = *Thalassinoides*

Figure 3 The out of phase amplitude which was exemplified by TAM-2 outcrop, interval 1800-2080 meter (see the general pattern of the in-phase amplitude in Fig. 5a and 5c).

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Figure 4 The in-phase amplitude which was exemplified by BER-2 outcrop, interval 2330-2650 meter (see the general pattern of the in-phase amplitude in Fig. 5b and 5d).

The other important result of PCA was PC scores of each ichnofabric units (see PC-1 and PC-2 scores in Table 4, in Arifullah et al., 2017). Each score could be plotted as curves (*i.e.*, PC-1 and PC-2 curves) which displayed the trending upward as well as in the wireline logging. Typically, the curves show the oscillatory pattern. PC-1 and PC-2 curves displayed out of phase amplitudes (Figure 3) and in-phase (Figure 4). In out of phase curves, typically shown the deviation between the curves, whether PC-1 in the left side and PC-2 in the right side or vice versa. By distribution, the out of phase amplitude curves was represented by PAL-3 and TAM-2 outcrops which generally located in the southern part of the research site.

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Figure 5 The typical PC curves in research site. The out of phase curves (a) and (c), and the in-phase curves: (b) and (d).

There was two pattern in out of phase amplitudes (Figure 5a and 5c). *First*, the PC-1 curves peak to the right side and the PC-2 curves peak to the left side (Figure 5c) displayed the situation when the higher of ichnodiversity, number of behavior and sediment disrupted and co-occurrence with small ichnofossil diameter and shallower penetration depth. The *Planolites*, *Paloephycus*, *Thallasinoides* assemblages commonly existed in this situation. *Second*, when PC-1 curves peaks to the left side and PC-2 curves peaks to the right side (Figure 5a) displayed the situation when the lower of ichnodiversity, number of behavior and lack of sediment disrupted and coincidence with bigger ichnofossil diameter and deeper penetration depth. The *Ophiomorpha*, *Skolithos*, and *Chondrites* assemblages are examples of that.

If PC-1 and PC-2 curves demonstrate the in-phase (Figure 5b and 5d), then the moving of both curves was harmony relatively. In this situation, PC-1 and PC-2 curves were in the same position whether on the left or right side. Moreover, no diagnostic

ichnofossils were founded. The in-phase amplitude was recognized in BER-1 and BER-2 outcrops which situated in the northern part of the research site. There were two oscillatory pattern curves in-phase amplitudes. *First*, both the PC-1 and PC-2 curves peaks to the right side (Figure 5b) displayed the situation when the higher of ichnodiversity, number of behavior and sediment disrupted and co-occurrence with wide ichnofossil diameter and deeper penetration depth. *Second*, when PC-1 and PC-2 curves peak to the left side (Figure 5d) displayed the situation when the lesser of ichnodiversity, number of behavior and sediment disrupted and co-occurrence with smaller ichnofossil diameter and shallow penetration depth.

5. Discussion

5.1 Colonization window

The concept of colonization window of Pollard et al., (1993) emphasize on time available for colonization or in another word as colonization chance. We suggest the chance corresponds to the complexity of ichnofossil (*c.f.*, Ekdale, 1985) that can be reflected by bioturbation index (BI), ichnodiversity (ID), the number of behavior (NB) (Arifullah et al., *in review*), penetration depth (PD) and ichnofossil diameter (Dm). Figure 2a and 2b displays the correlation between the variables.

According to PCA, we propose the colonization window is manifested by (1) PC-1 that composed by bioturbation index (BI) ichnodiversity (ID), and number of behavior (NB) are associated to the organism mobility (see Rhoads, 1975); (2) PC-2 that composed by penetration depth (PD) and ichnofossil diameter (Dm) is associated with the space use (see Bambach, 1983). As a result, refer to Bambach (1983), Miller (2003, 2007) and Bertling et al., (2006), we define that the ichnofossil system represents the ichnofossils that may grade laterally and vertically into coeval ichnofossil forming a logical association of ichnofossil elements.

5.2. Organism mobility (PC-1)

Biologically, the oscillatory PC-1 curve (Figure 3) may suggest the organism adopt a variety of behavior as conditions dictate, sometimes as a suspension feeder, sometimes as deposit feeder. Consequently, the ichnodiversity are changing during depositional processes. Those behaviors can create by a single organism (see Arthur et al., 1989). In addition, the interpretation of that features may be related to adaptation strategy of opportunist organism (see *e.g.* Ekdale, 1985) which may be regulated by the shifting of the physicochemical processes such as sedimentation rate (Goldring, 1964; Howard, 1978); water turbidity (*c.f.* Theede et al., 1969; Rhoads and Young, 1970) and paleo-oxygenation (Savrda and Bottjer, 1991) in the sediment-water interface. However, the further interpretation must be considered by surrounding paleoenvironmental conditions.

5.3 Space using (PC-2)

The biological interpretation will describe the meaning of PC-2 (Figure 2b). *First*, it may suggest the partition of the juvenile or adult organism which related to ontogeny processes (*c.f.* Levinton, 1977). Adult animal feed at a deeper tier with growth and reproduction seasonally than juveniles (Reise, 1979). In turn of those facts are only adult animal has the ability to penetrate deeply and survival from the environmental pressure of the sediment-water interface (see Arifullah et al., 2017). *Second*, it may be related to the

habitat partition of species. *Third*, facultative diminution which corresponds to brackish condition (Gingras et al., 2011).

Briefly, the fluctuation of the oscillatory PC-2 curves (Figure 4) may suggest the change the changes of turbidity process in the sediment-water interface (see Hubbard and Shultz, 2008) or deposition and erosion (see Goldring, 1964; Howard, 1978), paleosalinity (*c.f.* Sanders, et al. 1965) and paleotemperature (*c.f.* Johnson, 1965) and paleo-oxygenation (Savrda and Bottjer, 1991).

5.4 Paleoenvironmental cyclicality

The paleocyclicality of organism mobility (*i.e.* PC-1 curve) and space using (*i.e.* PC-2 curve) in the preceding paragraphs suggested the paleoenvironmental condition such as (1) frequency and rate of sedimentation; (2) water turbidity; (3) paleo-oxygenation; (4) paleosalinity and paleotemperature. Those paleoenvironmental conditions common occurred in tide-dominated depositional systems includes tide-dominated delta or estuarine (see Dalrymple and Choi, 2007). Consequently, paleoedeltaic origin in the study area (see Allen and Chambers, 1998; Bachtiar, 2004; Arifullah, 2005) can be inferred as tide-dominated delta or tide-dominated estuary.

In the out of phase amplitudes curves (Figure 3), the PC-1 curves peaks to the right side and the PC-2 curves peaks to the left side (Figure 5c) may suggest the domination of *paschichnia*, *repichnia* and *fodonichnia* behaviors which exemplified by *Planolites*, *Paleophycus* *Thalassinoides* assemblage. In other words, the organism mobility increase along with minimum space using. In another hand when PC-1 curves peaks to the left side and PC-2 curves peaks to the right side (Figure 5a) suggest the domination of *domichnia* which exemplified by *Ophiomorpha*, *Skolithos* and *Chondrites* assemblages. That is to say, the organism mobility decrease as well as in optimum space using. In addition, we speculate those phenomena are associated with epibenthic or endobenthic paleocommunity (see Ekdale, 1985).

In the in-phase amplitudes curves which PC-1 and PC-2 curves move in harmony (Figure 4). The PC-1 and PC-2 curves peaks to the right side (Figure 5b) may suggest the organism mobility increase along with optimum space using. In another hand when PC-1 and PC-2 curves peaks to the left side (Figure 5d) suggest the lesser organism mobility as well as minimum space using. No ichnofossil assemblages are the representation of this paleocyclicality.

6. Conclusion

Naturally, the generated curves (*i.e.*, in-phase and out of phase) demonstrate how the organism interacts with the substrate is as the respond of paleoenvironmental processes in the zone. The oscillatory pattern of the curve suggests how organism interact with the substrate are repeated that dictated routinely by the change of colonization window that dictated by paleoenvironmental processes. Regard to regional geology context, we argue that the curve pattern is related to the change of the intensity of fluvial, tidal, and wave processes that occurred in tide-dominated depositional systems. However, to justify it is delta and/or estuary depositional system must be proved by the indication of shoreline migration.

The generated curves may be unique as an indicator of the tide-dominated system if our methods are employed on other depositional systems (*e.g.* deep marine) also. Conjecturally, each paleoenvironmental condition is unique that characterized by the peculiar of the ichnofabric function of colonization window. Interestingly, the ichnofabric analysis in this paper is colored by (1) process - ichnological respond approach and (2) the using of the semi-quantitative method (*i.e.*, principal component analysis). Since the stressing on processes – ichnological respond, then the scrutinizing of bioturbation index,

ichnodiversity, number of behavior, penetration depth and ichnofossil diameter is made a point of in ichnofabric analysis.

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